

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Box 3.9: Assisted colonization

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Description

Box 3.9 reviews the invasion risks posed by assisted colonization – the deliberate introduction of species beyond their native range for the purpose of conservation of such species (e.g. when they are threatened by climate change) in Chapter 3 of IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control.

Process overview

Protocol

- Type of analysis/search/review: literature review

- Search language(s): English

- **Search terms:** ("assisted migration" OR "assisted colonization" OR "managed relocation" OR "conservation translocation") AND (invasi* OR nonnative OR alien OR nonindigenous OR exotic)

- **Search engine:** Web of Science

- **Date:** September 26, 2019

- **Searched time period:** 2000-2019

- **Selection criteria:** Expert scrutiny (inspection of abstracts) to remove papers that were inappropriate (such as those that concerned translocation of species within their native ranges).

- **Overview of the search results:**

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations): 10

- **Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):**

Number of papers reviewed: 21 (See [Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#))

Fields extracted:

- Publication title

- Year of publication

- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]

- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]

- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]

- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]

- **Files (code, review templates, etc.):**

[Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#)